

HIGH STRAIN RATE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON/GLASS AND
GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Thomas J. Frey ¹
Jack R. Vinson
Department of Mechanical Engineering
University of Delaware
Newark, Delaware 19716
and
Karl M. Prewo
United Technologies Research Center
East Hartford, Connecticut, 06108

ABSTRACT

Dynamic compressive mechanical properties have been determined experimentally and are presented for carbon/glass ceramic matrix composite materials and graphite/epoxy polymer matrix composites at strain rates varying from 100 sec.⁻¹ to 2000 sec.⁻¹. Very little or no high strain rate mechanical property data are available for the materials tested.

The carbon/glass ceramic matrix composite specimens were provided by United Technologies Research Center. The specimens tested included those with continuous unidirectional fibers with a fiber volume fraction of 50%, while others involved discontinuous randomly oriented fibers with a fiber volume fraction of 30%. The unidirectional graphite/epoxy material tested was provided by Thiokol Corporation and consisted of T40 graphite fibers in an ERL 1908 epoxy matrix, with a fiber volume fraction of 60%. These specimens were tested with fiber orientations in the 0° and 90° directions.

The measurements were made using the Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar facility at the University of Delaware. Measurements of yield strength, ultimate strength, elastic moduli and strain to failure were made at room temperature. Most properties were strain rate dependent, with some properties varying as much as 50% over the range of strain rates tested. It is hoped that the properties obtained will be of use as well as provide some insight into the behavior of these and similar materials at high strain rates.

¹ Now employed by Thiokol Corporation, Elkton, Maryland

1. INTRODUCTION

Material systems are usually characterized by their mechanical properties such as modulus of elasticity, yield strength and ultimate strength. Testing to determine these properties is normally performed in accordance with the American Society of Testing and Materials (ASTM) standards, which are typically at low or quasi-static strain rates (less than .01/sec). These properties are sometimes used by designers in analyzing structures subjected to environments which differ from the ASTM conditions.

There has been much research published which shows that for many metals the mechanical properties vary with strain rate (e.g., [1]). Various theories have been proposed to account for these effects. These theories include dislocation substructures [2], thermally activated mechanisms [3] and internal variables [4].

There has been less research published on the subject of high strain rate testing of composite materials. Much of the research indicates that composite materials also have properties which vary with strain rate. The Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) is widely used to conduct high strain rate tension, compression or torsion tests. The SHPB compression tests in this investigation consist of impacting a short cylindrical specimen between two long steel bars. The strain rates range from 100 to 2000/sec. Other high strain rate tests include drop [1], ring [5], liquid impact [6] and ballistic impact tests [7].

For the composite material systems chosen in this investigation there are little or no high strain rate test data available. Therefore, this investigation provides new insight into their behavior under high strain rate loading conditions and should be useful in the analysis of structures using these materials. This is important especially with the increasing use of composite materials in the aerospace industry. The material systems tested recently in this Department include aluminum, glass/polyester, graphite/-epoxy, carbon/glass and carbon/-aluminum. Only the graphite/epoxy and the carbon/glass results are presented herein.

The SHPB equipment is shown in Figure 1, [8]. Impact is initiated by releasing nitrogen gas from a pressurized chamber which causes the specimen to be impacted between the two bars. The striker bar is displaced on Teflon rings through the barrel where it strikes the incident bar (bar 1). The velocity of the striker bar V_{SB} just prior to impact is measured using two infrared beams set four inches apart.

Upon impact with the striker bar, the incident bar receives an elastic compressive strain wave with a wave velocity C_B and a wave shape $\epsilon_I(t)$ and is displaced along its length

axis. This bar is guided by Teflon bearings which are bolted to a steel I beam and secured on a reinforced concrete base to minimize vibration. When the wave reaches the bar 1-specimen interface, a portion of the incident wave is reflected back into bar 1 as a tensile wave with a wave shape $\epsilon_R(t)$. The remaining portion is transmitted into the specimen as a compressive wave. The wave transmitted into the specimen travels through the specimen and reaches the specimen-bar 2 interface, where a portion of the wave is reflected back into the specimen as a tensile wave. The remaining portion is transmitted into bar 2 as a compressive wave with a wave shape $\epsilon_T(t)$. This bar is displaced similarly to bar 1 but is caught after the test by a simple dashpot.

Because the specimen length is short compared to the bar lengths, the initial stress wave in the specimen undergoes numerous internal reflections during the test. It is calculated that the initial wave duration in a typical specimen is approximately two microseconds. Within a composite material specimen, there may be differences in the speed of the wave in the fiber and matrix materials. For clarity, these specimen internal reflections are not shown in the Lagrangian diagram of the SHPB equipment shown in Figure 2 taken from [9]. Due to the numerous reflections, the stress distribution along the specimen length is smoothed out and the specimen is assumed to be in a uniform state of stress at any instant [10]. The Lagrangian diagram shows that there is a characteristic time window corresponding to the duration of the wave pulses. This is defined as the time it takes a wave to travel the length of the striker bar and back. For the University of Delaware SHPB, the wave pulse time window is approximately 290 microseconds. Thus, to record information accurately at specimen failure, the specimen must fail within 290 microseconds after the start of the test.

Strain gages are mounted on bars 1 and 2 equidistant from the specimen interfaces and are connected to the oscilloscope. A third strain gage, mounted on bar 1 near the striker bar, acts as a trigger for the oscilloscope. The oscilloscope records the strain gages output as voltage versus time curves. A disk drive is connected directly to the oscilloscope and can store the data on a floppy disk. Using this data, the stress and strain versus time of the specimen during the test can be calculated.

2. DATA ANALYSIS

The data generated during each test are the two voltage versus time curves and the time taken by the striker bar to cross the two infrared beams. Measurements of each specimen's length and diameter must be recorded prior to the test. The details of analyzing the voltage versus time curves and a discussion of the computational equations and their use are given by Frey, Vinson and Hall [11] and Frey [12].

3. SPECIMEN MANUFACTURE

The carbon/glass (ceramic matrix composite) specimens were provided by United Technologies Research Center. One lot consisted of continuous carbon fibers with a fiber volume fraction of approximately 50% as detailed in [13]; the other lot consisted of discontinuous fibers with a fiber volume fraction of approximately 30% as detailed in [14]. The continuous fiber specimens were longitudinal as previously defined and were nominally 9.9 mm.(0.39") in length and 6.1 mm.(0.24") in diameter. The discontinuous fiber specimens have a random fiber orientation and were nominally 9.9 mm.(0.39") in length and 3.8mm.(0.15") in diameter. Because some of the specimens were damaged during shipment, it was decided not to attempt further machining. These specimens were tested in the as-received condition.

The graphite/epoxy material was provided by Thiokol Corporation in the form of a plate. The plate consisted of 100 plies of unidirectional prepreg of T40 graphite fibers in a ERL 1908 epoxy matrix cured in a standard autoclave. It was reported to have a fiber volume fraction of approximately 60%. The plate was cut into longitudinal and transverse prisms and machined on a lathe, using a cooling fluid.

4. GENERAL DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Because of the SHPB design, the true independent test variable is not the strain rate but the chamber pressure. While the pressure can be related to the strain rate, the relationship differs for each material system tested. In general, as the chamber pressure increases, the strain rate increases. The actual relationship can only be determined after analysis of test results. Thus, a test at 138KPa(20psi) may result in a strain rate of 500/sec for carbon/glass and 1000/sec for carbon/aluminum. Even within a single material system, five tests at 69KPa(10 psi) resulted in strain rates ranging from 498 to 699/sec for glass/polyester. The range of strain rates at a single pressure tended to decrease with increasing pressure. That is, the higher the pressure, the more consistent were the strain rates. This large range in strain rate for a single pressure can possibly be attributed to material variations from specimen to specimen and to mechanical losses. With the above noted, the SHPB test results are plotted as material property vs. strain rate.

Research has been conducted which indicates that specimen geometry, friction, inertia and dispersion effects may affect SHPB results. Davies and Hunter [15] report that the optimum specimen length to diameter aspect ratio for isotropic material (Poisson's ratio of 0.3) from inertial considerations is approximately 0.5 [16]. Vinson and Liu found that for

6061-T6 aluminum, varying the aspect ratio from one to two resulted in only a 6% stress variation at a strain rate of 1000/sec. It has been reported that even using a low friction coefficient lubricant like the molybdenum disulfide powder used in this investigation, frictional effects lead to an increase in apparent stress and resulted in errors in excess of 5% for aluminum specimens with a 0.25 aspect ratio [17]. It was also stated that the geometrical and frictional effects are coupled and may preclude the determination of an accurate modulus value. Another report found that the coefficient of friction may be neither constant over the specimen ends nor over the test duration due to variable specimen end surface finish and lubricant "jetting" [18]. Therefore, one must be cautious in extending these results to conditions other than as stated in this investigation.

Graphite/Epoxy

In figures (3) and (4) for the longitudinal graphite/epoxy specimens, it is seen that the ultimate stress is relatively constant at 1.72 GPa (250 ksi) over the strain rates tested (121 to 1944 /sec). This can be compared to the static value reported by Thiokol of 1.38 GPa (200 ksi). The ultimate strain appears to decrease 20% from .018 at 300/sec to .015 at 1400/sec.

As expected, the transverse specimen results exhibit a much lower ultimate stress than the longitudinal specimens. The transverse ultimate stress also appears to be independent of strain rate over the range tested (430 to 1971/sec) with an average value of 345MPa (50ksi). This can be compared to the static value reported by Thiokol of 37.9MPa (5.5 ksi). The transverse ultimate strain is significantly higher than for the longitudinal specimens and decreases with increasing strain rate from .032 at 500/sec to .018 at 2000/sec. These results are plotted in Figures (5) and (6).

Comparing the longitudinal to transverse specimen results shows that the longitudinal exhibit the typical fiber dominated properties of high strength and modulus and low strain, while the transverse exhibit matrix dominated properties. There appears to be a threshold strain rate of approximately 600/sec for both the longitudinal and transverse specimens below which both a yield and ultimate point are displayed on the voltage versus time curves and above which only an ultimate point is displayed. At the lowest strain rate, the longitudinal specimens appeared to fail by longitudinal splitting. At higher rates there was complete disintegration of the specimens. The specimen diameter increased (spread out) but the specimen did not fall apart. The transverse specimens fractured into several smaller pieces with fracture surfaces at an angle to the longitudinal axis. There appears to be a distinctly different failure mode for the two specimen types.

Carbon/Glass

Figures (7) and (8) show the results of the carbon/glass continuous fiber specimen tests. The ultimate stress increases with increasing strain rate from 1.03GPa(150 ksi) at 400/sec to 1.38GPa(200 ksi) at 1400/sec, while the ultimate strain appears to remain constant at .0125 in/in over the same strain rate range. Figures (9) and (10) show the results of the carbon/glass discontinuous fiber specimen tests. The ultimate stress increases with increasing strain rate from 1.03GPa(150 ksi) at 800/sec to 1.38GPa(200 ksi). The ultimate strain increases 50% from .0075 in/in to .015 in/in over the same strain rate range.

Comparing the continuous to the discontinuous fibers specimen results shows that the continuous exhibit a higher ultimate stress and modulus than the discontinuous at the same strain rate, as could be expected. At the lower strain rates, the discontinuous exhibits a lower ultimate strain, while at the higher strain rates, it is higher than the continuous. The continuous specimens exhibit a yield and ultimate point at strain rates below 510/sec but only an ultimate point at higher strain rates. The discontinuous fiber specimens exhibit only an ultimate point at all strain rates tested. The remains of the continuous fiber specimens show longitudinal splitting into dozens of small pieces while the discontinuous remains are in several larger pieces often with surfaces at an angle to the longitudinal axis. There appears to be a distinctly different failure mode for the two specimen types.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this experimental research, the effects of strain rate on material properties of several composite material systems were investigated using the SHPB apparatus. Over one hundred tests were conducted. The composite material fiber/matrix system test results included in this paper are for graphite/epoxy and carbon/glass. No previously published high strain rate mechanical property data was found on these particular material systems. A description of each material system and the specimen manufacturing process is contained in section 3. Details of the strain rate effects are contained in section 4. The major conclusions of this research are:

1. A significant difference between quasi-static and SHPB testing lies in the final fracture mode. Quasi-static testing generally produces either one or two fragments which may still possess residual strength. SHPB testing destroys all load carrying ability and produces almost total disintegration of the samples.

2. The SHPB apparatus can be used effectively to conduct compression tests on a variety of composite material systems to obtain mechanical property data and stress-strain relationships at strain rates ranging from 100/sec to 2000/sec.
3. Many of the mechanical properties of the materials tested were found to vary significantly with strain rate. This information can be used as a data base for improved designs of composite material structures subjected to high strain rate loading conditions.
4. Only by performing some experiments on new material systems, such as those treated herein, can insight be obtained to attempt to mathematically model the behavior observed. Much more investigation is needed.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Zukas, J.(ed.). Impact Dynamics. John Wiley and Sons, New York, N. Y.,1982.
- [2] Hartley, K. A. and Duffy, J."Strain Rate and Temperature History Effects During Deformation of fcc and bcc metals", Institute of Physics Conference Series, No.70, Oxford, England, 1984.
- [3] Ellwood, S., L. J. Griffiths, and D. J.Parry, "Strain Rate and Temperature Effects at High Strain Rates in AISI 321 Stainless Steel", *ibid*.
- [4] Kestin, J. A Course in Thermodynamics. Hemisphere Publishing, New York, N.Y., 1979.
- [5] Daniel, I. M., R. H LaBedz and T. Liber, "New Method for Testing Composites at Very High Strain Rates", *Experimental Mechanics*, February 1981.
- [6] Gorham, R. A. and J. G.Fields, "The Failure of Composite Materials Under High-Velocity Liquid Impact", *Journal of Physics (Applied Physics)*, 9, 1976.
- [7] Morris, A. W. H. and R. S. Smith, "Some Aspects of the Evaluation of the Impact Behavior of Low Temperature Fibre Composites", *Fibre Science and Technology*, 3, 1971.
- [8] Finch, W. H. *Compression Testing of Advanced Materials at High Strain Rates*. Master's thesis, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Delaware, 1988.
- [9] Yoon, H. S. *Dynamic Void Growth in a Non-Linear Viscous Solid*. PhD thesis, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Delaware, 1987.
- [10] Sierakowski, R. L. Dynamic Measurements of the Mechanical Properties of Filamentary Composites. *In Dynamic Response of Composites Materials*, SEM, 1985.

- [11] Frey T. J., J. R. Vinson, and I. W. Hall, "High Strain Rate Effects on Mechanical Properties of Glass/Polyester and Carbon/Aluminum Composite Materials", Proceedings of the 32nd AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, April 1991.
- [12] Frey, Thomas J. "*High Strain Rate Effects on Composite Material Properties*", Master's Thesis, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Delaware, 1990.
- [13] Prewo, K. M., "Carbon Fiber Reinforced Glass Matrix Composite Tensions and Flexure Properties", *Journal of Material Science*, 23, 1988.
- [14] Prewo, K. M., "A Compliant, High Failure Strain, Fiber-Reinforced Glass-Matrix Composite", *Journal of Material Science*, 17, 1982.
- [15] Davies, E. D. and Hunter, S. C. The Dynamic Compression Testing of Solids by the Method of the Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, 1963.
- [16] Rand, J. L. *An Analysis of the Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar*. Technical Report NOLTR67-156, United States Naval Ordnance Laboratory, 1967.
- [17] Sierakowski, R.L., Private Communication, 1989
- [18] Gorham, D. A., P.H. Pope and O. Cox, "*Sources of Error in Very High Strain Rate Compression Tests*", Inst. of Physics Conf. Series No. 70, Oxford, England, 1984.

Figure 1: University of Delaware SHPB Equipment

Figure 2: Lagrangian Diagram for the SHPB Equipment

Figure 3: Ultimate Stress Versus Strain Rate-Graphite/Epoxy

Figure 4: Ultimate Strain Versus Strain Rate-Graphite/Epoxy

Figure 5: Ultimate Stress Versus Strain Rate-Graphite/Epoxy (transverse)

Figure 6: Ultimate Strain Versus Strain Rate-Graphite/Epoxy (transverse)

Figure 7: Ultimate Stress Versus Strain Rate-Carbon/Glass (continuous)

Figure 8: Ultimate Strain Versus Strain Rate-Carbon/Glass (continuous)

Figure 9: Ultimate Stress Versus Strain Rate-Carbon/Glass (discontinuous)

Figure 10: Ultimate Strain Versus Strain Rate-Carbon/Glass (discontinuous)

